

Metabolic and Physical Variables of Wheelchair Basketball Players with Upper Limb Polio and Spinal Cord Injuries: Relationships to the Functional Classification System

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Abstract—The Functional Classification System is based on the movements that wheelchair athletes can make when playing wheelchair basketball. However, when these athletes have upper-limb polio, it makes this system difficult to use, because this disease no longer exists in all but a few countries. However, in Brazil, more than 50% of wheelchair athletes had polio, and it is difficult to classify them using the existing system. The objective of this research is to improve the Functional Classification System and to test its efficacy. This research used comparisons of metabolic and physical evaluations (medicine ball throw test, hand grip strength test, and 20-meter speed test) of wheelchair basketball players with spinal cord injury and players with upper-limb polio, and relates these results to the Functional Classification System. This was a transversal study, with a sample of 18 athletes. Group 1 was comprised of seven athletes with upper limb polio. Group 2 was comprised of eleven athletes with spinal cord injuries. Data from the athletes with upper limb polio were collected in Recife, at the State University of Pernambuco. Data from the athletes with spinal cord injury were collected in São Paulo, at the Federal University. All subjects were compared using the following variables: Ergoespirometry with adapted treadmill to measure pulmonary gas exchange during exercise (VO_2 , VCO_2 and FC), medicine ball throw test, hand grip strength test, and 20-meter speed test. For the statistical analysis, we used the Mann-Whitney test ($p < 0.05$). The results for Group 1 and 2 are as follows: Group 1, medicine ball throw = 294.19 cm; 20-meter speed = 6.28 s; hand grip strength right and left hands = 34.11 Kg/f and 42.11 Kg/f, respectively; and Group 2, medicine ball throw = 395.78 cm; 20-meter speed = 5.52 s; hand grip strength right and left hands = 58.64 Kg/f and 56.41 Kg/f, respectively. For the test of adapted treadmill, greater gas exchanges (VO_2 , VCO_2 , FC) were observed in Group 2 as compared with Group 1. These results demonstrate that the Functional Classification System that was applied to these athletes must be reconsidered, since it does not agree with the metabolic and physical data from these groups.

Key Words: Wheelchair basketball, Functional Classification System, Polio.

Introduction

Wheelchair basketball is a sport that began during the Second World War, at Stoke Mandeville Hospital, England, with Dr. Guttman, and in the USA with Dr. Lipton, when the governments of these countries tried to improve the rehabilitation of soldiers wounded in the war (Strohkendl, 1996).

The exercise of wheelchair basketball was impressive, because it permitted the rehabilitation of people relative to bio-psycho-social aspects. The game began to be organized into clubs and played widely. The growth of the sport has been rapid and spontaneous, with the creation of new teams, including state championships and national and international games, as well as the Paralympics (IWBF, 2002).

The result of a dispute between teams, it was necessary to create the system of Functional Classification, in 1999. After many experiments to find an ideal system, the International Wheelchair Basketball Federation (IWBF)

created one system with five classes (1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 4.5), in which each team of five athletes would accumulate a maximum of fourteen points. This was good for the game, giving a dynamic aspect to its athletes and making it possible for people with different kinds of physical disabilities to play with equality (IWBF, 2002).

Much research has been performed relative to the process of functional classification and the physical variables of athletes. Bednarczyk & Sanderson (1993), completed a study that compared the Medical Classification, the first model of classification, with the actual classification (i.e., Functional Classification System). They concluded that the Functional Classification is better than the others because it does not affect the objectives of game.

In another study, Malone, Gervais, and Steardward (2002), analyzed the factors that have influence on the three-meter-throw for different functional classes in wheelchair basketball. The results demonstrated that the functional classes 1.0 and 2.0 have more difficulty than the other classes

(3.0, 4.0 e 4.5), because the athletes in classes 1.0 and 2.0 did not have lower trunk muscle control.

In countries that created the system of Functional Classification (Australia, Canada, and the USA), polio was eradicated at the end of '70s, so the classifier system was created based on spinal cord injury and for amputee athletes, and adapted for athletes with polio (Labanowich, 1997; Strohkendl, 1996; Quadros, 1997).

However, in Brazil, according to Ferreira (1999), more than 50% of wheelchair athletes had polio, including polio that affected the upper limbs, making it more difficult to establish functional classifications (Ferreira, 1999), which are essential to international championships.

This research used comparisons of metabolic and physical evaluations (medicine ball throw test, hand grip strength test, and 20-meter speed test) of wheelchair basketball players with spinal cord injury and with upper limb polio, and relates these results to the Functional Classification System. The general objective was to analyze the physical variables (power, force, and speed) and metabolic variables (VO_2 max, VCO_2 max and FC max) for these athletes.

Hutzler (1993) analyzed the physical variables of nine athletes from the National Israel Team using the arm cranking and field test (428 meters circuit). Four of these athletes had polio that affected the lower limbs.

Rotstein et al. (1994) performed a study of the aerobic and anaerobic capacities of eight athletes using arm cranking, and one of them had polio that affected the lower limbs.

In 1999, Vanlandewijck, Daly, and Theisen assessed aerobic and anaerobic capacities using field tests (25 meters circuit test and 20 meters circuit test) in 46 athletes. Four of them had polio.

In 2001, Knechtle used an adapted treadmill to study eleven wheelchair basketball athletes, two of whom had polio.

In all of these studies, the number of athletes with polio was small, and all had polio that affected the lower limbs. Thus, the current research was undertaken for its relevance to Brazilian athletes.

Method

This was a transversal study. The sample included 18 male athletes: seven in Group 1 had polio that affected the upper limbs; 11 in Group 2 were athletes with spinal cord injuries. Their ages ranged from 18 to 49 years, and their functional classifications ranged from 1.0 to 3.5.

Data from the athletes with upper limb polio were collected in Recife, at the State University of Pernambuco. Data from the athletes with spinal cord injury were collected in São Paulo, at the Federal University.

All subjects were compared relative to the following variables: ergoespirometry with adapted treadmill, measure pulmonary gas exchange during exercise (VO_2 , VCO_2 and Fc max), medicine ball throw test, hand grip strength test, and 20-meter speed test.

For the ergoespirometry the athletes started the test at a velocity of 2 km/h, during two minutes for training. Then, the velocity increased at the rate of 1km/h each minute until it was over. Before starting the test the athletes were told that they would have to give their maximum efforts.

This kind of protocol was chosen because most researchers prefer to work with the protocol that increases velocity rather than inclination, because the latter may be dangerous for athletes who may slip (Mello, 2002).

For the medicine ball throw, one medicine ball 5kg was used, with tape measure and tape fixed to the floor. The athletes sat on the floor with their backs near the wall. The researcher measured the distance of the throw between the wall and the first contact of the medicine ball with the floor. The athletes made three throws and afterwards the measurement was made (in centimeters).

For the hand grip strength test, the athlete sat in his own wheelchair, with his arm extended behind his body. Two trials were performed, reversing the right and left hands after the measurement was taken (measure unit in Kg/f).

A tape measure with three positions, 0, 10, and 20 meters, was used to measure the speed at 20 meters. At each position a person with a special clock marked the time. The athlete started at position 0, and when the researcher said "Now," he began to run as fast as possible.

This research was approved by the Ethics Research Committee of the University of Brasília (UnB), and athletes signed a document of consent.

Results

For the statistical analysis, we used the Mann-Whitney test ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1 illustrates that the mean age of the two groups was similar, 30 years old. The athletes with polio had lower weights and heights than the athletes with spinal cord injuries.

For Group 1 (athletes with polio), the comparative results of the other variables were: medicine ball throw = 294.19cm; 20-meter speed test = 6.28 seconds; ergoespirometry = maximum speed = 9.43 minutes; VO_2 max = 2.36l/min, VCO_2 max = 3.20 l/min; Fc max = 185.57 bpm, with a total time of 08:58 minutes; handle pm, right = 34.11 Kg/f, left = 42.11 Kg/f).

The results for Group 2 (athletes with spinal cord injuries) were: (medicine ball throw = 395.78cm; 20 meters speed test = 5.52 seconds; ergoespirometry = maximum speed = 11.91 minutes; VO_2 max = 2;20l/min, VCO_2 max = 3;03l/min, Fc max = 181.82bpm, with a total time of 11:20 minutes; hand grip strength test, right = 58.64 Kg/f, left = 56.41 Kg/f).

These results demonstrated that the functional classification of these athletes must again be evaluated, because the mean for the functional classes was greater in the polio group (Group 1) than in the spinal cord injuries, and this is not in agreement with these results.

Table 1. Variables of athletes with polio and spinal cord injury.

Group	Tests	Variable	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Polio, Group 1 (N=7)						
		Age	29.14	5.49	20	36
		Weight	62.40	11.02	49	80.30
		Height	167.43	6.70	158	178
		Functional Class	2.14	1.02	1	3.50
	Hand Grip Strength	Right	34.11	22.61	1	50
		Left	42.11	14.03	23.5	64
	Medicine Ball Throw	Medicine ball	294.19	52.45	215	385.33
	Speed	10 meters	3.44	0.4	3.04	4.27
		20 meters	6.28	0.85	5.07	7.64
	Ergoespirometry	Max. Heart Rate	185.57	10.64	168	199
		VO ₂ Max	2.36	0.56	1.8	3.1
		Time 1	6:43	1:49	4:3	10:01
		Speed 1	7.29	1.98	5	11
		CO ₂ Max. Volume	3.2	0.76	2	4.5
		Time 2	6:40	1:5	4:5	10:06
		Speed 2	7.14	2.04	5	11
		Test Duration	8:58	1:46	6:34	11:4
	Speed	9.43	1.72	7	12	
Spinal Cord Injuries, Group 2 (N = 11)						
		Age	30.	9.21	18	49
		Weight	66.87	10.59	45	80.3
		Height	173.36	5.9	158	180
		Functional Class	2.04	0.87	1	3.5
	Hand Grip Strength	Right	58.64	8.88	37	68.25
		Left	56.41	8.79	36.5	70.75
	Medicine Ball Throw	Medicine ball	395.78	33.56	351.66	459
	Speed	10 meters	3.27	0.38	3.01	3.99
		20 meters	5.52	0.71	4.58	6.52
	Ergoespirometry	Max. Heart Rate	181.82	10.63	162	194
		VO ₂ Max	2.2	0.41	1.6	2.9
		Time 1	10:03	3:15	5:2	14:49
		Speed 1	10.55	3.21	6	15
		CO ₂ Max. Volume	3.03	0.74	1.8	4
		Time 2	10:32	3:01	6:01	14:49
		Speed 2	11.09	3.02	7	15
		Test Duration	11:2	2:44	7:43	15:49
	Speed	11.91	2.63	8	16	

Table 2. Test of Mann-Whitney for right hand grip strength.

Mann-Whitney test	
Hand Grip Strength, Right Hand	
Statistic	33
Normal Distribution (Z)	-2.9949
One-tailed Test (Pr<Z)	0.0014
Two-tailed Test (Pr> Z)	0.0027

Table 3. Test of Mann-Whitney for left hand grip strength.

Mann-Whitney test	
Hand Grip Strength, Left Hand	
Statistic	42
Normal Distribution (Z)	-2.1736
One-tailed Test (Pr<Z)	0.0149
Two-tailed Test (Pr> Z)	0.0297

Table 4. Test of Mann-Whitney for medicine ball throw.

Mann-Whitney test	
Medicine Ball Throw	
Statistic	34
Normal Distribution (Z)	-2.8996
One-tailed Test (Pr<Z)	0.0019
Two-tailed Test (Pr> Z)	0.0037

Table 5. Test of Mann-Whitney for 20-meter speed test.

Mann-Whitney test	
20-meter speed test	
Statistic	90
Normal Distribution (Z)	2.0841
One-tailed Test (Pr<Z)	0.0186
Two-tailed Test (Pr> Z)	0.0372

Discussion

The problem that motivated this study began at the World Championship Junior Subdivision 23, held in the city of Blumenau, SC, Brazil, August 21st, when international functional classifiers assigned Brazilian athletes to the classes 1.0 and 3.0 after making only visual inspections, and without any tests. This fact was unfavorable for positioning the athletes in the game and to all team members. It affected the athletes negatively, both psychologically and physically.

After this event, Brazilian classifiers began to look for new information, but were unable to find new scientific articles about athletes with polio. The explanation for this was simple: other countries did not have these types of athletes. So, it became necessary for the Brazilian team to develop its own research.

In order for athletes to play wheelchair basketball, they must generate force, speed, and power. Therefore, this research attempted to determine the differences between these key variables in athletes with upper limb polio, and athletes with spinal cord injuries. The athletes with polio scored a greater classification value, and this disagrees with the physical and metabolic values of the research.

Cooper (1992) studied eleven spinal cord injury athletes with the hand grip strength test to obtain antropometric values. The values were 55Kg/f for the right hand, and 54 Kg/f for the left hand. No statistical difference was found between them.

In 2004, Gorla et al. measured the force of upper limbs in wheelchair basketball athletes and in [non-disabled] non-athletes. One of the tests was the hand grip strength test. The values demonstrated that the wheelchair athletes were stronger than the non-athletes.

Gorgatti and Bohme (2000) studied 20 persons: 10 wheelchair basketball athletes and 10 non-athletes, with the objective of analyzing their upper limb power. The analysis

employed the medicine ball throw. The mean values were 520 cm for the athletes and 380 cm for the non-athletes.

Hutzler et al. (1998) used the Wingate test to assess upper limb power in three different kinds of athletes: those with spinal cord injury, polio, and amputees. The results demonstrated that lower back injury paraplegic athletes and those with polio showed smaller values than the amputee athletes and those with polio with legs affected.

Barros, Costa, and Ramos (2004) used the Wingate test for 30 seconds with two groups, one with spinal cord injuries and another with polio affecting the upper limbs, and found that in the group with polio the mean was 368.08 watts. In the other, the mean was 500.56 watts. So, the polio group had more difficulty in the test and showed less power.

Brasile (1986a, b) validated the test of speed at 20 meters for wheelchair basketball, an adaptation of the speed at 50 meters test, created by Johnson and Nelson in 1979, with the objective of analyzing the speed of these athletes.

Vanlandewijck, Daly, and Theisen (2000), used the 20-meter test with the objective of testing specific abilities by wheelchair basketball athletes. Forty-six athletes participated in this study, including 13 with spinal cord injuries, 4 with polio, 12 amputees, 10 "other type of injury," and 7 without physical disabilities. The scores presented by these athletes were 5.92 seconds for a first trial, and 6.22 seconds for a second trial.

Doyle et al. (2004) used the speed at 20-meter test to analyze 46 athletes. Their objective was to compare the results with functional classifications. The mean of 4.6 seconds was scored by both classes 2.0 and 3.0.

In 1998, Schimid et al. investigated 30 female wheelchair basketball athletes and 10 non-athletes, using an adapted treadmill. The results demonstrated that the group of athletes had a higher respiratory capacity ($VO_2 = 6.21$) than the group of non-athletes ($VO_2 = 4.71$).

Knechtle & Koppfli (2001) compared two protocols, one with growing inclination, and the other with growing speed on an adapted treadmill. Eleven wheelchair basketball athletes were the subjects of the study. The results did not demonstrate a significant statistical difference between the two protocols.

Vanlandewijck, Spaepen, and Lysens, in 1994, analyzed metabolic variables and propulsion in 40 wheelchair basketball athletes, using an adapted treadmill. They compared the results with functional classifications. The results in the metabolic variables showed a significant statistical difference for the different classes, but no statistical difference was found for the propulsion variable.

As we know, the Functional classification System relies directly on movement performance of athletes with physical disabilities, however, it also seems to have a relationship with the general physical performance.

In this study, the measured metabolic and physical variables were greater in athletes with spinal cord injury than in athletes with polio, although their functional classifications scores did not agree with these results.

Conclusion

These results demonstrate that the Functional Classification System must be reconsidered, since it does not agree with the metabolic and physical data from all kinds of physical disabilities, particularly the group with upper limb polio.

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